

GAMIFICATION AND DIGITALISATION OF EDUCATION**Moshynska O.***Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor
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The education system is undergoing fundamental transformations. Along with the technologies of presentation of material by teachers to students, the timing of lessons, not designed for different levels of perception and concentration of attention, will also change. It is believed that in time, the traditional accumulation of knowledge in the form of grades will be abolished and the learning process will be modernised through new, advanced digital solutions and gamification. Gamification and digitalisation of education is the use of gaming elements in learning to make it more interactive engaging for learners. This can include the use of game mechanics such as assignments, points, achievements, levels, etc. Successful implementation of information technologies in educational processes will help to bring the sphere of education in Ukraine to a new level.

Keywords gamification, information technology, digital game, digitalisation, education.

Summarizing the opinions of experts and studies, we can say that the pandemic has affected the quality of education, but at the same time it has performed a mobilizing function for its digitalization. The meta-trend (acceleration of all changes) of recent years is online education and its two main components, among which are personalisation of learning and interactivity. Automatic personalisation makes it possible to adapt the learning process depending on each person's abilities, her desired learning speed and behavioural characteristics. An individual educational trajectory is formed for a specific information portrait of the student. And for this purpose, machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms are applied. Interactivity allows students to use different senses and get emotions, contributes to the effective assimilation of information. This is achieved through virtual reality, augmented reality and gamification.

In Ukraine, digitalisation and gamification in education has been gaining popularity for several years, especially in the field of online learning. Some online courses already use elements of gamification to help students better digest the material and motivate them to learn it. Back in 2021, the SELFIE project was launched in Ukrainian schools - a tool for assessing the effectiveness of digital technology implementation in educational institutions. Teachers and students from different regions told in a survey what digital devices are used in schools, what technical support is available today, and so on.

For example, gamification can be used to activate cognitive activity. And today it is necessary to teach this to teachers. During lectures, you can break them down into various interactive stories, which are very easy to create by choosing a suitable service in the cloud. Ordinary smartphones are suitable for use in the classroom, you don't even need a computer lab for this. In addition, gamification allows you to introduce elements of competition into the learning process, to compare your results with the results of other participants in the educational process. Finally, it is impossible not to mention such a form of student co-operation as collective performance of tasks, project activities in virtual teams, competitions between these teams and so on.

To create a gamification system it is necessary to take into account 5 main components: to create a goal for the user: so our product makes sense, and the user gets pleasure from the fact that they have completed the task; to write rules: they should be easy to understand and you-execute; to describe feedback: during the passage it is necessary to show the user the result of his activity, that we have not forgotten about him and follow his success; to create motivation: it is necessary to explain to the user that for the time and effort spent, he will be rewarded; to add a reward for the time and effort spent by the user; to add a motivation: it is necessary to explain to the user that he will be rewarded for the time spent by the user.

Students find it difficult to assimilate the material that is read during one lesson monotonously and without the use of multimedia technologies (video, presentations), they get tired and, as a consequence, do not want to learn something that makes them bored, therefore it is difficult to keep their attention. It is necessary to dilute the lesson, some game or presentation, which interests them to study more deeply this subject. When they are interested: time passes faster, they stop feeling as if they are in the class and are engaged in studying the issue more thoroughly, together. Communication also plays a big role here, it is better to unite people and give them the opportunity to learn and work together, so they learn to work in a team.

According to the International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, gamification in education increases student performance by 34.75% [3]. According to forecasts, the number of computer classes in schools will increase. The global video game industry is currently a dynamic industry.

In general, the digitalisation of education in Ukraine represents a significant investment for the government and is seen as a necessary measure to improve the quality of education in the country and prepare students for the challenges of the digital era.

Gamification of education can be a powerful tool to engage students and improve their learning outcomes. However, the cost of implementing gamification can vary greatly from country to country and from one educational system to another [4].

However, it is important to note that the cost of gamification is not limited to technology and software. Teachers and administrators also need to be trained on how to use gamification effectively, which may require additional resources and funding. In addition, ongoing maintenance and upgrades to gamification systems can also incur ongoing costs.

Ultimately, the cost of gamification in education will depend on many factors, including the level of technology required, the size and complexity of the educational system, and the resources available in a particular country or region. As resources, there are already ready-made educational technology tools specifically designed to incorporate gamification strategies into the learning process. For example, Quizizz, Kahoot, Socrative, Duolingo, MyQuiz and many others can help teachers turn any subject into a game. Other apps, such as Minecraft: Education Edition, allow students to co-operate with their peers in a game world related to the topic they are discussing in class. Games are not a complete replacement for a full education in schools, colleges and universities, but they are a worthy addition to support and enhance learning. They can be implemented: board games, video games, etc.

It is also possible to earn with the help of educational technologies on platforms and resources. For example, adding special rates (with discounts), subscription for a small fee, advertising, training programmes not only for schoolchildren and students, but also for employees of companies and government agencies.

The education market is quite vast. Gamification should be carried out taking into account the characteristics of the audience: level of education (pre-school, school, higher or additional specialised education), purpose of learning (foreign languages, hobbies, applied skills, consolidation and/or expansion of skills). Not every game may be suitable for a certain group of learners. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the approaches to gamification and to adapt the content to the situation. Approaches are ways of applying game elements to non-game situations. Structural. Its essence is to add new game elements to familiar teaching methods. For example, developing a rating and giving students points for completing tasks in a regular class. Content. In this case, completely change the content and the way of presenting educational material. For example, make up a story and give students roles. In both cases, it is important not to deviate from the main goals and to maintain adequate competition between participants.

The giants of online learning: Google Yandex Coursera.org (and others) have long ago moved away from the format of a classic lecture of 2 academic hours and split into lecture 'chunks' of 3 to 25 minutes. This way students don't get tired and absorb information better, and many colleges and universities use gamification techniques such as Achievements and leaderboards to encourage students to participate in school activities, motivate them to learn more outside of the classroom, and foster more interaction with peers. Other universities are also using gamification to teach soft skills and to help students form lifelong learning habits. These experiments with gamification have shown that they not

only improve student motivation and success, but also improve retention.

In the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), the assessment of competences is a top priority, which has contributed to the restructuring of teaching and learning methods, putting students at the centre of attention. These methods involve students' active participation in the learning process, including in class assignments, which provides lecturers with important information about the extent to which students have mastered the given competences. In this scenario, gamification techniques play a central role. For example, in the study of law, 'Moot Courts' and simulations have become the preferred practices. This goal is achieved through the following specific tasks: familiarising students with the elements and process of preparing to create a moot court or simulation (defining rules, topics, timing, selection of material, etc.); gaining an understanding of the different options for conducting a moot court or simulation; exploring different options for evaluating the results of a Moot Court or simulation. [5]

Summarising the above we can highlight the advantages and disadvantages of gamification.

Gamification is useful for education because: it increases a person's self-confidence. If something failed, there is an option to try again and succeed; it allows students who hold back their potential in traditional learning to open up; it unites and allows them to sincerely rejoice in achievements; it helps to explore different characters of people through characters and avatars; it creates comfortable conditions, most students behave actively and openly; due to intrigue, it increases involvement; it gives an opportunity to think outside the box; it develops a sense of responsibility for the result, teaches to interact in a team; it helps to adapt to the situation in the world. Due to its ease and unobtrusiveness, gamification creates a need for knowledge and development. This need is explained from the physiological point of view. The anticipation of success and reward stimulates the production of dopamine. When memorising information, serotonin is produced, which is also responsible for a positive emotional background.

The disadvantages include dependence on external motivation, i.e. gamification can create a dependence on external rewards rather than promote internal motivation. Over-reliance on technology and lack of individualisation can also be noted as disadvantages of this system. Gamified systems may not effectively cater to the individual needs and learning styles of all students.

Thus, it can be concluded that despite some disadvantages gamified systems are the future, everything for the digital generation is intuitive and user-friendly. When students are involved in a gaming situation, they are offered educational content, it works very well. And, on the other hand, such inclusions in the learning process allow for changing activities, which always influences cognitive activity. Digital technologies help educators to get a little closer to 'digital' children. When a teacher comes to the classroom and faces something that is not very clear to him, students can teach him, give him a hint. And this is not to be feared, it's a normal story. But the teacher knows the subject area and knows how to combine it with digital technologies,

and his students are still a long way away from that. Yes, teachers and lecturers are used to being number one, especially if they are university professors and founders of scientific schools. But you just have to admit that you don't know something and ask: 'Help me...' This is a new direction - co-operative learning, co-operative activity.

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